

A Study on Influence of Working Environment on Teaching Efficiency of Primary School Teachers Working in Different Schools of Kathua District.

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Abstract:

A work environment is the settings in which a person works. It includes the social environment as well as physical conditions of that place which impacts the feelings of wellbeing, workplace relationships and efficiency of the persons working over there. The teacher has a major role in educational development whether he approaches his work actively or passively and for teaching efficiently the teacher must have a good positive working environment. This study aims to quantitatively assess the influence of working environment on teaching efficiency of primary school teachers working in different schools of Kathua district. In the study a sample of 120 teachers (60 males and 60 females) was selected from different primary schools of Kathua district. Teacher effectiveness scale and Work environment scale was used to collect data. Mean, Standard Deviation, Standard Error Deviation, t-test and ANOVA were calculated for the analysis of data. The findings of the study shows that there is interactional effect of good, average and poor work environment on teaching efficiency of teachers.

Keywords: Efficiency, Influence, Effectiveness, t-test, ANOVA, Interactional.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Research is a scientific approach of answering a research question, solving a problem or generating new knowledge through a systematic and orderly collection, organization, and analysis of information with an ultimate goal of making the research useful in decision-making. Systematic research in any field of inquiry involves three basic operations-

1. Data collection: It refers to observing, measuring, and recording information.

2. Data analysis: It refers to arranging and organizing the collected data so that we may be able to find out what their significance is and generalize about them.

3. Report writing: It is an inseparable part and a final outcome of a research study. Its purpose is to convey information contained in it to the readers or audience.

In this context, legal research is defined as ‘systematic’ finding law on a particular point and making advancement in the science of law. It involves a systematic search of legal materials, statutory, subsidiary and judicial pronouncements. For making advancement in the science of law, one needs to go into the ‘underlying principles or reasons of the law’. These activities warrant a systematic approach. An approach becomes systematic when a researcher follows scientific method. Research is systematic, because it follows certain steps that are logical in order. These steps are-

- Understanding the nature of problem to be studied and identifying the related area of knowledge.
- Reviewing literature to understand how others have approached or dealt with the problem.
- Collecting data in an organized and controlled manner so as to arrive at valid decisions.
- Analysing data appropriate to the problem.
- Drawing conclusions and making generalizations.

This research study has clearly shown that effective teachers are key to students learning over the past several decades, having effective teachers has been consistently identified as the most important school-based factor in improving students’ academic achievement. The research has proved that teacher effects have long-run consequences for their student’s success. An effective teacher understood that teaching involves multiple tasks to ensure that all students receive a quality education. Teachers are identified as an important source of variability in student achievement.

Although recruiting knowledgeable and skilled teachers is important, it is insufficient for schools to ensure effective teaching performance. Good teachers need a work place that promotes their efforts in a variety of ways to rating their effective teaching and doing their best work with students. Teachers working condition play an important role in a school to deliver high quality education. Schools that are able to offer their teachers a safe, pleasant and supportive working environment can better attract and retain good teachers and even motivate them to do their best. Generally it covers a broad range

of factors and issues, from working time security to remuneration, as well as the physical conditions and mental demands that exist in schools.

1.1 Education:

Teaching learning process is as old as human being on earth. It has been carried out by human being and even by animals to teach their young ones for successful adjustment in the environment. Education is a process of human enlightenment and empowerment for the achievements of better and higher quality of life. In a democratic country like India the role of education is extremely crucial. Democracy requires that the entire person should be educated. Education is an important national activity. It is the backbone of a country's progress. Success of democracy depends on its citizens. Hence, democracy needs citizen to be educated.

“Education is a process, a social function carried on and by the society for its own sake”.

Man is a social animal and the education plays an important role throughout his life. No civilized society is believed possible for an individual to be fit for adult life if he does not have some degree of formal education. It has universally been accepted that prosperity of a nation is also reflected in its educational system. Quality of a nation depends upon quality of its people and economic growth but both depend upon quality of education, the fact remains same that the most important factor in the education process is the teacher. The teacher is the key of any educational reconstruction.

“If a student is to be prepared for evolving world, then an essential attribute of a competent teacher is awareness of the world”.

The teacher should be an integrated individual, skilled in the art and science of human relations and conscious of the wide variety of behavior patterns in the world to which he may have to adjust. Adjustment is not a simple term like adaption is accommodation. It is actually a condition or a state of mind and behavior in which one feels that one's need have are will be gratified those of who can adopt are adjust to all needs of changing conditions can live happily and successfully. The development of a nation depends upon their students and the all over development of a student depends upon his teacher. Only a teacher develops the capacity among the children for adjusting in home,

school and society. As the education Commission 1964-66 has lightly pointed out “the destiny of the country is being shaped in her class rooms.” Evidently the commission has in mind the role of the 2 teacher in realizing the goal of national reconstruction. Teachers have important role to play in shaping the further generation. The role of the teachers in democratic system of education is very crucial. They have to act as friends, philosophers and guides of the students, and help them to march forward to establish a new social structure. The role of the teachers in molding the personality of the students depends on the aims of education. It is the responsibility of the teachers to develop the physical, mental, social, emotional, intellectual and aesthetic aspects i.e. total personality of the students.

Vivekananda said, “Education is the manifestation of divine perfection, already existing in men.” He wanted that the aim of education should be man-making.

It is good that educationalists and educational planners in India have started realizing that only securing enough teachers will not do, as what is equally important is securing the right type of teachers. Teacher is the most vital factor in the system of education. Education Commission 1952-53 also point out, “Every teacher and educationalist of experience knows that even the best curriculum and the most perfect syllabus remain dead unless quickened into life by the right methods of teaching and right kind of teachers”.

Moreover, effective and productive learning on the part of students can be achieved by employing teachers with desirable attitudes or by shaping their attitudes in the desired direction. Until and unless teachers with positive frame of attitude are engaged in the teaching profession, no drastic results can be expected from them.

- **Need of Education**

The new born infant is helpless human being. He has neither any friend nor any enemy. He is not aware of the social customs and traditional. But as he grows elder, he is influenced by the formal and informal agencies of education. In this way they develop physically, mentally, emotionally and socially. Education guides him like an affectionate father and serves him faithfully like a wife. Education helps in developing the individual like a flower, which distributes its fragrance all over the environment. Education drags a person from darkness, poverty and misery by developing his personality in all areas.

Education also contributes a lot to the growth and development of society. Through education moral ideas, spiritual values and cultural heritage are transferred from one generation to another for preservation, purification and sublimation into higher and higher achievements.

1.2 Working Environment :

A positive psycho-social content helps to create a conducive environment for effective teaching and learning. Quality teaching and learning are supported when school professionals plan, develop, institute, monitor and assess the characteristics of a positive psycho-social school environment. These components include: positive student and teacher relationships, violence prevention in school, disciplinary interventions that promote student socio-emotional development, maintaining reasonable workloads, and helping students see the value and purpose of learning beyond the classroom content and grades.

A healthy and safe physical school environment promotes learning by ensuring the health and safety of students and staff. The physical school environment encompasses the school building and its contents, the land on which the school is located, and the area surrounding it. A healthy school environment will address a school's physical condition during normal operation as well as during renovation (e.g. - ventilation, moisture, temperature, noise and natural and artificial lighting), and protect occupants from physical threats (e.g. crime, violence, traffic and injuries), and biological and chemical agents in the air, water or soil as well as those purposefully brought into the school.

1.3 Teaching:

Teaching is a social process, it is influenced by both the political and social backgrounds of the country.

According to Gage, Teaching is a form of interpersonal influence aimed at changing the behavior potential of another person.

Edmund Amidon defined it as "Teaching is an interactive process, primarily involving class room task which takes place between teacher and pupil and occurs during certain definable activity.

J. S. Brubacher “Teaching is an arrangement and manipulation of a situation in which an individual will seek to overcome and from which he will learn in the course of doing so”.

Skinner- Teaching is the arrangement of contingencies of reinforcement.

1.4 Teaching Efficiency:

Efficiency means doing things right. A teacher can exhibit efficiency in the manner he/she gets things done he/she manages his/her class and his/her time in getting things done. A good example wherein a teacher can be called efficient is when he/she always comes to his/her class (and leave) on time, with well-prepared lesson plan, instructional materials, engaged time on task and everything is organized regardless of output or result produced in the teaching learning process.

But a teacher is efficient when she gives her best in teaching and able to make her students learn or master the skills and turned them meaningful, relevant and applicable in real life situations. Efficiency means doing things right while effectiveness is doing the right things. These two concepts should complement each other because it's hard to be an effective teacher if you are not efficient.

1.5 Measurement of Teacher's Efficiency:

A student's perception of a teacher's efficiency might be based on observations of lessons. Speed with which homework is corrected and returned. A teacher's self-perception of his/her efficiency might be based on some other criteria. A school principal's perception of a teacher's efficiency might be based on submitting curriculum plans, test results, school reports etc. on time to meet school determined deadlines. Various methods may be used to measure teacher's efficiency. Summated rating scales could be used to measure student perception.

Observations by trained observers over a few lessons could be used to measure practical teaching skills. Open-ended questions put to a school principal might be a useful source of information. We may also follow the following methods.

1. Assessing from the teaching method and techniques.
2. By getting the feedback from the students.
3. By MCQ questionnaires.
4. Personal interest in the particular subject.

5. Appearance of the teacher and his attitudes.

Accordingly to V. Jayshree outcome of a teacher can be measured by two ways.

- **Qualitative observations:**
 - a. Attitude of the teacher- positive attitude, proactive or no sincerely, consistency, love towards the profession.
 - b. Initiative in teaching learning- interest in preparation for theory and practical's and delivery.
 - c. Initiative taken in extended learning
- **Quantitative bests:**
 - a. Feedback from only eligible students who are sincere and have real urge for learning.
 - b. Feedback from stake holders.

Effectiveness and efficiency of teacher depends upon a number of variables. Availability of suitable working condition is one such factor. A large number of primary schools didn't have basic facilities like drinking water, sanitary, playground etc. some school also have no adequate facilities like Amirah, boxes and libraries etc. Availability of instructional materials in primary schools remain limited. Student in schools with better facilities have high level of achievement.

The elementary level, the root of education is facing very harsh problems as wastage and stagnation. In order to remove them, professionally committed and emotionally intelligent teachers are required. Keeping this view the investigator will attempt to study the influence of Emotional Intelligence and Professional Commitment on Teacher Effectiveness at elementary level. An ingredient of a successful organization is a healthy dose of emotional intelligence. As noted by Goleman, at the individual level, emotional intelligence can be identified, assessed, and upgraded. Because the responsibilities of teachers are to incorporate programs that enable students to learn, to cope, understand their own value, gain empathy for others, and manage and control their emotions.

These factors of emotion, this insight into oneself as well as into the emotions of others, constitute the first step in gaining essential skills for a successful life. Professional commitment plays a decisive role in effective teaching. The more a teacher is committed,

the more he would acquire competencies and the more he would tend to be performing teacher. Professional committed teachers are required in order to increase the quality of elementary education. This fact motivated to the researcher to study the effect of emotional intelligence and professional commitment on teachers effectiveness. Only emotionally intelligent and Professionally Committed teachers inculcate above described traits among students. Teachers can facilitate learning by molding the behavior they expect learners to demonstrate in every aspect of life. The behavior of a teacher is crucial for the transfer and maintenance of new emotional and social competencies. Teaching strategies should address different learning styles and incorporate visual, sensory, auditory, and interactive elements such as role-playing, group discussions, and simulations, special recommendation is the use of self-disclosure in which teachers use their own stories to communicate how they deal with an emotion. Sharing stories that reflect the teacher's self-awareness, motivation and persistence provides a model of behaviour that learners can emanate in their own efforts to form mutually satisfying relationships and become more emotionally strong.

1.6 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY:

It is unanimously accepted by eminent scholars and researchers of different fields such as educationists, sociologists, psychologists, policy makers, politicians, administrators etc. that in our country there is an unprecedented need for successful teachers to lead the multitudes of school children and adolescents. Successful teachers can contribute significantly to the process of improving education. The explosion of knowledge at very fast pace is bringing about economic, social, political and technological upheaval in the country. These in turn is reflected in the classroom teaching and necessitate the requirement in the classroom teaching of a competent and effective teacher. The teacher has a major role in educational development whether he approaches his work actively or passively. He can influence development adversely by opposing innovations or merely remaining mute in the face of a growing need for reform. On the other hand he can participate actively as an initiator himself or on interpreter of the plans devised by others. The lack of professionalism and supply of poor teachers are the two points effecting he quality of teaching in the country. It is a matter of deep thought and observation that why do the nation lack dedicated teachers who feel proud in introducing themselves as

"teachers". The academicians and researchers have tried to establish relationship between the subject knowledge and teaching success.

It was almost unanimously accepted that teachers with better academic records acquire success in teaching and become better teachers. But vast observation make it very clear that only knowledge of subject matter, teaching skills and awareness towards job are not enough for successful teaching. This in turn gives rise to another question that what are the qualities and characteristics associated with successful teaching? Various studies listing characteristics of successful and unsuccessful teachers have been carried out. These researchers found some common characteristics among effective teachers i.e. sympathetic, sense of humor, patience impartial, pleasing manners, polite, broad minded, intelligent and strong character besides the knowledge of subject matter and teaching skills.

1.7 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

Teacher's workload is also an important aspect of working conditions which effect their work efficiency. Poor working condition and heavy workload lead to stress, anxiety and frustration. The primary school teacher working in rural areas have to work under difficulties and pitiable conditions. Hence, an explanative study was undertaken to find out the influence of working environment on teaching efficiency of primary school teachers working in different schools of Kathua district.

The study in hand may be stated as:

Influence of working environment on teaching efficiency of primary school teachers.

1.8 OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS OF THE TERMS USED:

- **Work Environment** - The term **work environment** is used to describe the surrounding conditions in which an employee operates. The work environment can be composed of physical conditions, such as office temperature, or equipment, such as personal computers. It can also be related to factors such as work processes or procedures.
- **Teaching Efficiency** - Efficiency of a teacher refers to measure of success of teacher in carrying out institutional and other specific duties by the nature of his/her position. Teacher's efficiency includes strategies of instruction, student and

classroom management, inter personal relationships, preparation and planning for teaching, knowledge of the subject matter and teachers' characteristics. Efficiency is the quality of being successful in producing and intended result.

1.9 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To study the mean difference of teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Good and Average work environment.
- To study the mean difference of teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Good and Poor work environment.
- To study the mean difference of teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Average and Poor work environment.
- To Study the interactional effect of Good, Average and poor work environment on teaching efficiency of Primary School Teachers.

1.10 HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY:

Ho₁: There is no significant mean difference on teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Good and Average work environment.

Ho₂: There is no significant mean difference on teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Good and Poor work environment.

Ho₃: There is no significant mean difference on teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Average and Poor work environment.

Ho₄: There is no interactional effect of Good, Average and Poor work environment on teaching efficiency of Primary School Teachers.

1.11 DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY:

The present study is delimited to following areas.

- The present study is limited to Kathua Districts of Jammu.
- The study confined to 20 Primary Schools suitable Kathua District of Jammu.
- The present study is confined 60 male and 60 female Primary School teacher total 120 Sample.
- The present study confined into two variables – Work Environment, Teaching efficiency.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

A literature review is an evaluative report of information found in the literature related to the selected area of study. The review should describe, summaries, evaluate and clarify this literature. It should give a theoretical base for the search and help the author in determining the nature of his research. Works which are irrelevant should be discarded and those which are peripheral should be looked at critically.

A literature review is more than the search for information, and goes beyond being a descriptive annotated bibliography. All works included in the review must be read, evaluated and analyzed. Relationship between the literatures must also be identified and articulated in relation to the field of research.

In writing the literature review, the purpose is to convey to the reader what knowledge and ideas have been established on a topic and what their strengths and weaknesses are. The literature review must be defined by a guiding concept.

2.1 PURPOSE OF LITERATURE REVIEW.

In general, the literature review should

- Provide a context for the research.
- Justify the research.
- Ensure the research hasn't been done before
- Show where the research fits into the existing body of knowledge.
- Enable the researcher to learn from previous theory on the subject.
- Illustrate how the subject has been studied previously.
- Highlight flaws in previous research.
- Outline gap in previous research.
- Show that the work is adding to the understanding and knowledge of the field.

2.2 STUDIES RELATED TO TEACHER'S EFFICEINCY

- **Sodhi, Binakshi (2010)** conducted a research work on Teacher effectiveness of secondary school teachers of Punjab in relation to school organizational climate. The present study was undertaken with the objectives: To study teacher effectiveness among secondary school teachers of Punjab in relation to their school

organizational climate, gender, location, teaching experience and stream (science, social science and languages). A sample of 75 senior secondary schools (45 rural and 30 urban) were selected. Further all the teachers' newline (totally 450) working in these schools were administered research tools, namely school organizational climate, teacher effectiveness scale, teacher attitude inventory and job newline satisfaction scale. It was concluded that the secondary school teachers perceiving autonomous and familiar type of school newline organizational climate have exhibited significantly higher level of teacher effectiveness as compared to those perceiving school climate to be of closed type. There is no significant difference in teacher effectiveness of secondary school teachers across gender, location, stream and teaching experience groups.

- **Riti (2012)** conducted a research work on a study of teacher effectiveness in relation to school organizational climate and administrative behaviour of school heads of Himachal Pradesh. In the process of education, teacher plays the biggest role. So, the teacher must be quite effective to accomplish the goal of education. The teacher effectiveness is likely to be influenced by many factors. School Organizational Climate and Administrative Behaviour of the school heads could be two of such factors. Therefore in the present study the teacher effectiveness is studied in relation these two factors. 60 Government Schools from three districts viz. Solan, Una and Bilaspur from Himachal Pradesh state were taken up for the study. A sample of 350 teachers at secondary level and all the 60 school heads was drawn from these schools. Three tools were used; (i) Teacher Effectiveness scale by UmmeKulsum (2000). (ii) School Organizational Climate Description Questionnaire by M.L. Sharma (1978). (iii) Administrative Behaviour Scale by HaseenTaz (1998). The results of the study showed that (i) Different types of school organizational climate existed in different schools. Controlled type of school organizational climate was the most prevalent in the schools. (ii) Teacher effectiveness of teacher teaching in urban schools was found to be significantly higher than that of teachers teaching in rural schools. (iii) No significant difference was found in the teacher effectiveness between male and female teachers. (iv) The teacher effectiveness significantly differed in schools with different types of school organizational climate. The mean teacher effectiveness score was highest in case of open school organizational climate. (v) There was a significant difference in the

administrative behaviour of school heads across different school organizational climate. (vi) Administrative Behaviour had a significant and positive effect on the teacher effectiveness.

- **Aina Jacob Kola, Olanipekun Shola Sunday and GarubaIsmaila Ayinde (2015)** conducted a research work on Teachers Effectiveness and its Influence on Students' Learning. The research abstract published on Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal Vol.2, No.4. The main thrust of this review is the perceived central position of professional focus to the effectiveness of any category of teacher in Nigeria According to literature, indicators like) instructional delivery students' assessment, learning environment, teachers' personal)quality, motivation, and subject content knowledge among others were used to measure teachers' effectiveness. Distraction, professional development, interpersonal relationship and punctuality were seen as essential components of professional focus that determines teachers' effectiveness. Recommendations suggested were based upon these components of professional focus.
- **Danielle Simmons Banister (2015)** conducted a research work on A Correlational Study of Teacher Effectiveness: Evaluation Instrument and Value-Added Model. This correlational study was conducted to determine the relationship between two measures of teacher effectiveness in a southeastern state in the United States. The state utilizes a teacher evaluation instrument that rates teachers based on principal observations on five standards. Additionally, a sixth standard is populated with data from a value added model that measures a teacher's impact on student learning based on student achievement on standardized tests. This study aimed to compare methods used to assess quality teaching. As the teacher has the greatest impact on student achievement, educational agencies and districts have focused efforts on improving teacher performance. However, there currently is not a single instrument that stakeholders agree would quickly and accurately assess teacher effectiveness, necessitating the investigation of evaluation systems and processes for identifying effective teaching. Research was collected in a large, urban school district in the state to determine the relationship between the two measures within the context of a single school district. The value-added data and the state teacher evaluation instrument data were analyzed among the teachers of tested subjects in Grades 4-12 in the school district to determine if there was a correlation between

the ratings provided by each of the measures. Spearman's rank-order coefficient was used to analyze the relationship between scores. The results demonstrated were negligible to weak correlations between the teacher evaluation instrument standards and EVAAS scores. Limitations, recommendations, and implications for future research were included with the findings.

- **Umasankar Dash &Pranab Barman (2016)** conducted a research work on Teaching Effectiveness of Secondary School Teachers in the District of PurbaMedinipur, West Bengal. The research abstract published on IOSR Journal Of Humanities And Social Science (IOSR-JHSS) Volume 21, Issue 7, Ver. VII (July. 2016) PP 50-63. -Effective Teaching is an art and no easy endeavour. Generally Teaching is delivered by a teacher to enhance the amount of learning of a learner. To make learning more meaningful, understandable and fruitful to a learner, effectiveness of teaching delivered by a teacher is very essential condition. Through the present study an attempt has been made by the investigators to study the level of Teaching Effectiveness of Secondary School Teachers in the district of PurbaMedinipur, West Bengal. The investigators have used Descriptive Survey method for the present study. In this study, Teaching Effectiveness of Teachers has been evaluated by their concerned students. The sample consists of 100 Teachers who were working in different Secondary Schools in the district of PurbaMedinipur. The Stratified random sampling technique has been used for the selection of sample. The investigators have developed a Scale by themselves to measure the level of Teaching Effectiveness of Teachers on the basis of Likert's five point scale i.e. Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. For the analysis of data Mean, S.D., t-Test, ANOVA and Graph have been used by the investigators in the present study. The results of the study explore that the Overall level of Teaching Effectiveness of Secondary School Teachers is good in the district of PurbaMedinipur. It is also revealed that though there is no significant difference among the Secondary School Teachers regarding their level of Teaching Effectiveness on the basis of Gender, Stream, Training Status and Qualification, but it is found that there is significant difference among the Secondary School Teachers regarding their level of Teaching Effectiveness on the basis of School Location.

- **Titus M. Owoh (2016)** conducted a research work on Teacher Effectiveness as Correlate of Students' Cognitive Achievement at Upper Basic Education in Basic Technology. The research abstract published on Journal of Education and Practice, Vol.7, No.29, ISSN 2222-1735. This study sought to find out the relationship between students perception of their teacher effectiveness and academic achievement in Basic Technology. Teacher's personality, teaching techniques/classroom management strategy and appearance, all integrate to make for teacher effectiveness. To carry out this research, two research questions and one null hypothesis guided the study. The design of the study is a correlational survey. The population for the study comprised the entire 823 two Upper Basic (UB) students of Basic Technology in Upper Basic schools in Udi LGA. While 442 (53.7%) students constituted the sample. Means, Pearson's product moment correlation statistics were used in analyzing the data, which were generated at two levels. Level one was the mean perception score and the second level was the student achievement score. Based on the analysis the following findings were made. There is a low mean perception of students of Basic Technology on their teacher effectiveness. There is positive relationship between their mean perception and their academic achievement. This relationship was found to be significant. Recommendations were made based on the findings among which is that teachers and their trainers should be further trained through workshops and seminars.
- **Genevieve Wanjala and Edwin Wanjala (2017)** conducted a research work on Level of Teachers' Efficiency in Work Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Wajir North District, Kenya. The research abstract published on International Journal of Scientific Research and Innovative Technology ISSN: 2313-3759 Vol. 4 No. 4; April 2017. The purpose of this research was to determine teachers' efficiency levels in work performance in public secondary schools, Wajir North District. We had three research objectives based on teachers' level of lesson preparation, utilization of teaching-learning time and classroom management strategies as monitoring tools for efficiency in the provision of education. The study employed descriptive survey research design in which questionnaires, classroom observation schedules, observation checklists and document analysis were used as instruments for data collection. The sample size was 283 comprising 3 head-teachers, 30 teachers both of whom were purposively sampled and 234

students who were randomly sampled. 16 classrooms were observed. Data collected were analyzed using appropriate descriptive statistical methods the research findings indicate that teachers mostly prepared for lessons but did not utilize teaching-learning time well. The study has also established that classroom management strategies used were inappropriate and recommends for the inclusion of in-service training programs in educational planning.

- **Rupnar, Santoshi Halder and Sen Malay Kumar (2017)** conducted a research work on Teacher Effectiveness and Related Characteristics: A Systematic Review. The research abstract published on The Online Journal of New Horizons in Education - January 2017 Volume 7, Issue 1. During last two decades, numerous researchers have been studying related characteristics of Teacher Effectiveness. In order to arrive at and identify the research gap on the area of the proposed study, a systematic review of related literature was conducted on ‘Teacher Effectiveness and its related characteristics’. For systematic review, certain definite steps were followed to survey the related literature. First, in planning stage, ‘Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria’ were defined to identify the related literature systematically. Secondly, in the review stage, ‘Summary of the Findings’ were analyzed and discussed after recording the identified studies in a ‘Systematic Review Table’. Thirdly, in the final stage, ‘Research Gap’ was identified in the field of present investigation. Only those studies which were published between the years of 1990 to 2015, were included. For searching the related literature, only the computer based online Internet searches were conducted through the Search Engines mentioned above (see Table 1). Only the studies which performed Survey type researches with large samples based on Person related and Categorical variables, were included and identified for systematic review. By searching with several permutations and combinations of the Key words through the Search Engines, related 244 studies were collected. With respect to the criteria 116 studies were excluded and finally 128 studies were selected and gathered in the pool of systematic table (see Table 2).
- **Bhat Raj Lakshmi (2017)** conducted a research work on A Study of Teaching Effectiveness of Prospective Teachers in Relation to Stream and Gender. The research abstract published on Amity International Journal of Teacher Education (AIJTE), Volume 3, No.1, April 2017. In the present investigation an attempt has

been made to study the effect of Pre service teacher education on teaching effectiveness of Prospective teachers in relation to their gender and stream. The sample consisted of 200 Pupil teachers of central universities of Delhi. The teacher effectiveness scale developed and standardized by Ummekulsum was used. The results show that the Impact of pre-service teacher education training on teaching effectiveness of the pupil-teachers was found to be significant at 0.01 level of confidence. There was no significant effect of gender on teaching effectiveness of the pupil-teachers. It was found that effect of stream on teaching effectiveness of pupil-teacher was significant.

- **JhaNeelima (2018)**-conducted a research work on Teacher Effectiveness in Relation to Professional Commitment and Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers of Lucknow. It is generally agreed that the effectiveness of an educational program to a large extent is dependent on the effectiveness of teachers. A school may have excellent material resources – equipment, building, library and other facilities along with a curriculum appropriately adopted to suit the need of community, but if the teachers are indifferent to their responsibilities, the whole educational program is likely to be ineffective and wasted. The National Policy on Education (1986) has rightly remarked, ‘No system of education can rise above the level of its teachers.’ An effective teacher may be understood as one who helps in the development of appropriate knowledge, skills, desirable attitude, adequate personal and social adjustment, empathy and sensitivity towards fellow beings and sound value system of the learners. A teacher who is an effective facilitator in the balanced development of competencies related to Cognitive, Affective and Psychomotor domain. The teachers are responsible for the quality of the product coming out of schools and colleges. To shoulder this responsibility it is important that teachers remain committed to the profession, be lifelong learners and also derive satisfaction from their work so that they can become efficient and effective facilitators of learning. The present study is undertaken with a view to find out ‘Teacher Effectiveness in Relation to Professional Commitment and Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers of Lucknow.’ The sample of the study consisted of Seven Hundred and Thirteen Secondary School Teachers of Lucknow city from Seventy (ICSE, CBSE and UP Board) schools. Out of which two hundred and sixty two male teachers and four hundred and fifty one female teachers were

selected. Three standardized tools were used to collect the data – Teacher Effectiveness Scale by Pramod Kumar and D. N. Mutha, Professional Commitment Scale by Ravinder Kaur, Sarbjit Kaur Ranu and Sarvjeet Kaur Brar, and Job Satisfaction Scale by Meera Dixit. The analysis of the data revealed that there is positive and significant relationship between Teacher Effectiveness and Professional Commitment, between Professional Commitment and Job Satisfaction and between Teacher Effectiveness and Job Satisfaction. This shows that Teacher Effectiveness, Professional Commitment and Job Satisfaction are related to each other.

- **Radha Rani Roy and Ujjwal Kumar Halder (2018)** conducted a research a work on Teacher Effectiveness: A Self-Report Study on Secondary School teachers. The research abstract published on Research Gate, Volume 5, Issue 3, E ISSN 2348 – 1269, PrintIssn 2349-5138. The present study was conducted on 400 teachers of secondary schools in three selected districts in West Bengal. The teaching effectiveness was estimated by a self-rating scale, namely Jayaraman’s Teacher Effectiveness Scale (JTES) developed by Jayaramanna. The secondary aim of this study was to explore the differences in teaching effectiveness of the secondary school teachers in terms of their gender, locality of the schools and their designation. In case of gender and locality of the schools, it was found that teachers are not different in their strategies of teaching aspect and social aspect of teaching effectiveness. But, in personal aspect, professional aspect, intellectual aspect of teaching effectiveness and after all in teaching effectiveness itself, the teachers differed significantly due to their gender and the locality of the schools. In case of the designation, teachers showed differences in all the aspects of teaching effectiveness and also in teaching effectiveness.

Improving Quality and Efficiency of Education Dr. Radhika Kapur(2019) – It is necessary for the principals, heads, educators and other members to pay adequate attention towards bringing about improvements in the quality and efficiency of education. With advancements taking place and with the advent of globalization and modernization, it is necessary to improve quality and efficiency of education. Improving quality and efficiency of education would enable the individuals to satisfactorily achieve academic goals and enhance the standing of educational institutions within the community. Furthermore, the educators will incur the feeling

of job satisfaction, develop motivation towards the implementation of their job duties and feel pleasurable within the working environment. Furthermore, students would also feel pleasurable and develop interest and enthusiasm towards enriching their academic performance. The main areas that have been taken into account in this research paper are, strategies implemented by teachers to improve quality and efficiency of education, additional ways to enhance quality and efficiency of the system of education, and improving quality and efficiency of education through effective administration.

- **Dr. Radhika Kapur (2019)** conducted a research work on Improving Quality and Efficiency of Education. It is necessary for the principals, heads, educators and other members to pay adequate attention towards bringing about improvements in the quality and efficiency of education. With advancements taking place and with the advent of globalization and modernization, it is necessary to improve quality and efficiency of education. Improving quality and efficiency of education would enable the individuals to satisfactorily achieve academic goals and enhance the standing of educational institutions within the community. Furthermore, the educators will incur the feeling of job satisfaction, develop motivation towards the implementation of their job duties and feel pleasurable within the working environment. Furthermore, students would also feel pleasurable and develop interest and enthusiasm towards enriching their academic performance. The main areas that have been taken into account in this research paper are, strategies implemented by teachers to improve quality and efficiency of education, additional ways to enhance quality and efficiency of the system of education, and improving quality and efficiency of education through effective administration.
- **Muhammad Akram (2019)** conducted a research work on Relationship between Students' Perceptions of Teacher Effectiveness and Student Achievement at Primary School Level. The research abstract published on Bulletin of Education and Research August 2019, Vol. 41, No. 2 pp. 93-108. The purpose of this study was to measure the relationship between teacher effectiveness score and student achievement at primary school level. Using the multistage sampling technique, 40 high schools (20 male and 20 female) were selected as strata. Later, all 2000 students of grade 9 of these 40 schools in District Okara were sampled. A School Teacher Effectiveness Questionnaire (STEQ) Developed and validated by Akram

(2018) was adopted for this study to measure teacher effectiveness. The STEQ was found to be highly reliable ($\alpha=.88$). Student achievement scores in English and Mathematics of these students were also collected from respective schools. Pearson correlation was used to measure the relationship between teacher effectiveness and student achievement. The study found moderate positive significant relationship between teacher effectiveness score and student achievement. Learning environment demonstrated highest relationship with student achievement in English and Mathematics, followed by effective communication. Multiple regression analysis revealed that 32 percent of variance in student achievement in English and 12 percent of variance in student achievement in Mathematics was explained by teacher effectiveness scores. Further, male and female students did not significantly differ on their perceptions of their teachers' effectiveness. The study provides evidence of validity and reliability of STEQ leading the idea that primary school students can validly measure teacher effectiveness scores. Limitation includes private tuition that can contribute to student achievement. The study implied that student ratings can be used as a supplement data source of measuring teacher quality.

2.3 AN OVERVIEW:

The review of related literature presented an overview of studies related to Work Environment and teaching effectiveness. A close perusal of the review of studies revealed that work environment has been studied in relation to environments, personality performance, Job Satisfaction, Employees' Performance, etc. Teaching effectiveness has been studied in relation with Organizational climate, Administrative behaviour, Student's learning, Evaluation instrument, Professional commitment, Student's achievement etc. The review of literature suggested that variables i.e Work Environment and Teaching Effectiveness have been studied either independently or in combination with other variables or in terms of their interaction with various other factors. It has been found that, studies related to Influence of Work Environment on teaching effectiveness of the students has not been undertaken so far. So, this study will help to open the door to a new and different venue for the study Work Environment and Teaching Effectiveness. The study conducted by the investigator was a sincere attempt to understand the influence of Work Environment on teaching effectiveness of the student.

3. METHODOLOGY:

Research Methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problem. It may be understood as a science of studying how research is done scientifically. This chapter presents the description of research methods used in this study. This chapter provides information about the area of study, research approaches, research design, targeted population, sample size and sampling procedure, sampling techniques, types of data, data collection methods and instruments, data analysis procedure, with this the ethical issues, privacy confidentiality and consideration also presented in this chapter

3.1 RESEARCH DESIGN:

A research design is the arrangement of conditions for collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to the research purpose with economy in procedure. The research design is the conceptual structure within which research is conducted. It constitutes the blue print for the collection, measurement and analysis of data. Suitable research design chosen for this study was descriptive research design. Descriptions can be concrete or abstract. Descriptive research includes surveys and fact-finding enquiries of different kinds. The major purpose of descriptive research is description of the state of affairs as it exists at present. In social science and business research, we quite often use the terms Ex-post facto research for descriptive research studies. The main characteristic of this method is that the researcher has control over the variables, he can only report what has happened or what is happening. The methods of research utilized in descriptive research are survey methods of all kinds, including comparative and correlation methods.

3.2 POPULATION:

Population or universe means, the entire mass of observation which is the present group from which a sample is to be formed. The sample observation provides only an estimate of population characteristics. The term "population or universe" conveys a different meaning than a traditional one but in research methodology population means the characteristics of specific group.

In this study, all the Primary School teachers from Government and Private schools of Kathua district of Jammu formed the population of the study.

3.3 SAMPLING:

Sampling is the most important aspect of any necessary study. It is impossible for any researcher to collect data about the whole population. So he has to select the small portion, which is the true representative of the whole population.

The idea of sampling is quite old, though the theory of sampling has developed in recent years. The main object of sampling technique is to draw conclusions about the whole by examining only a part of it.

“A sampling as the name implies, is a smaller representation of a larger whole.”

-Good &Hatt.

“A statistical sample is a miniature picture of cross-section of the entire group or aggregate from which the sample is taken. The entire group from which a sample is chosen is known as the population.” **-P.V. Young.**

(a) SAMPLE SIZE:

It is not possible to deal with the whole population in the studied area, therefore a portion of the population selected to participate is important. The sample represents the actual characteristics of the whole population involved in the study. It has been reported that if a small representative sample is drawn from the entire population. The parameters are represented and estimated by the sample statistics. In this present study, the investigator selected a sample of 120 teachers in which 60 males and 60 females were included from 20 different primary schools of Kathua District of Jammu.

(b) SAMPLING PROCEDURES AND TECHNIQUES

Sampling is the process of selecting study unit. The resulting group of respondents is a sample-sampling is the procedure used to select sample, place or thing to study in the target area. It is the process of selecting a sub group from a large population with elements necessary for study. There are two common sampling procedures named probability sampling and non-probability sampling. The probability sampling occurs when there is possibility of selecting each elements as a sample. The non-probability sampling refers to the case where the probability of including each element of population in a sample is unknown. In this study simple random sampling was used to choose the study sample.

3.4 TOOLS USED:

The following tools were used for the study:

3.4.1 Teacher effectiveness scale developed by Pramod Kumar and D.N.

Mutha- Initially, the Teacher Effectiveness Scale consisted of 69 items solicited on the basis of previous studies. These items belonged to the following teaching behaviour categories (i) Information source, (ii) Motivator, (iii) Disciplinarian, (iv) Advisor and guide, (v) Relationship with pupils., fellow—teachers, principals and parents, (vi) Teaching skill, (vii) co-curricular activities, (viii) Professional knowledge, (ix) General appearance and habits in relation to class-room, (x) Class-room management, and (xi) Personality characteristics.

Justification of using Teacher Effectiveness Scale-As possibly we could see teaching effectiveness as an element within the wider notion of teacher efficiency, so research used Teacher Effectiveness scale to fulfill her research objectives.

Scoring Procedure:

All the 69 items of the scale are positively worded. Items are given a score of 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 for strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree respectively. The sum of these values gives the teacher-effectiveness score for the subject. The total score varies from 69 to 345, showing least teacher-effectiveness to highest teacher effectiveness.

Reliability: The split-half reliability (correlating the odd/even items) for the scale, applying the Spearman-Brown formula is found to be .67 (N100) with an index of reliability of .82.

The test-retest reliability of the scale is also studied. It is found to be .75 (N=50) with an index of reliability of .85. with two months interval time (Kumar &Mutha, 1974). The r-values have been found to be significant at 0.01 level, showing the scale is highly reliable both in terms of its internal Consistency and stability of scores. Showing Split Half and Test-Retest Reliability

Reliability	N	r-value	Index of Reliability
Split-half	100	0.67	0.82
Test-retest	60	0.75	0.86

Validity: Only highly discriminating items are included in the scale. The upper 27% and lower 27% served as criterion groups (Garrett, 1961). Discriminating value of each item has been determined by calculating C .R. on the basis of the responses of upper and lower groups.

The face validity of the measures is fairly high. The content validity is ensured as the items for which there has been 100 per cent agreement amongst judges regarding their relevance to teacher effectiveness are included in the scale. Further, the scale has been validated

against principal's ratings. The correlation between principal's rating and self-rating is found to be .77 (N50), with an index of reliability of 0.87.

Showing Correlation between Principal's Rating and Self Rating

N	r-value	Index of Reliability
50	0.77	0.87

Percentile Norms Separate percentile norms for the male and female teachers are given in the tabel. These are to be interpreted in the conventional manner.

Percentile	Male (N=300)	Female (N=100)	Effectiveness Categories
90	326.91	329.91	Most effective
80	313.21	315.81	
75	311.81	312.91	More effective
70	307.71	310.63	
60	299.91	302.72	Average
50	293.47	295.39	
40	285.72	287.31	
30	276.03	278.03	Low effective
25	271.80	273.81	
20	265.61	269.32	Least effective
10	250.00	254.01	
Median	293.47	295.39	

DATA COLLECTION METHODS AND INSTRUMENTS

No single method of data collection instrument can provide wither best data or reliability and validity of data collection tools. In this study questionnaire and documentary literature reviews were used for collecting data.

3.4.2 Perceived Work Environment scale was developed by Dr. S. M. Khan - This measure is designed to help researcher and practitioners in assessing the current state of given work environment.

The PWES provides measures of 11 empirically derived dimensions of perceived work environment, which are –

1. Effectiveness of Supervision / Management.
2. Working Condition.
3. Confidence in Management.
4. Monetary Gain.
5. Sociability & Cooperation with Employees.
6. Opportunity for Growth & Development.
7. Sense of Belongingness with the Organization.
8. Citizenship Behavior & Recognition at Work.
9. Working Relation.
10. Employees Benefit Programmes.
11. Job Stress.

In this scale there are 46 items distributed in the 11 dimensions having 38 positive and 08 negative items. This is a five point Likert scale each items have five alternatives Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree, Strongly Disagree.

S.N.	Type of Items	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
i	Positive	5	4	3	2	1
ii	Negative	1	2	3	4	5

The test sheets were scored as per scoring system given in scoring system 2. To make scoring easy

Indicate Negative Items.

The range of score on the scale is 46-230.

Reliability: one of the most commonly used reliability coefficient i.e. Cronbach’s Alpha was calculated and was 0.93, significant at 0.001 level (Khan & Pandey 2002). The internal consistency of the scale is quite high and this gives a support that the scale is reliable. Inter- correlation among dimensions of the scale are given 11 dimension.

Validity: Content (Face and logical) validity of the English/ Hindi version of the scale was by professional psychologists/ academic psychologists/ technical Instructors (numbering about 10 experts) of Psycho-Technical Directorate, RDSO (Ministry of Railways), Department of Psychology, University of Lucknow and Zonal Training Centers of Indian Railways. Good Correspondence was found to exist between the scale results and the considered judgments of experienced observers in three the railway zones (Central, Northern and Western) at a sample of 275 Drivers, validity was established by conducting nondirective interviews.

3.5 STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES:

“Statistical is the mathematical technique or process of gathering describing, organizing, analyzing and interpreting numerical data since, research Yield these quantitative data statistics is the basic tools of measurement and research”.

Statistical methods help in drawing inferences on the characteristics of the population on the basis of the sample. Statistics is thus an important tool in designing research, analyzing its data and drawing conclusions there from.

To analyze the interpret the test scores, the investigator has used following statistical techniques.

1. **Mean:** - mean is often referred to as average. It is the central value of a series which is representative and which may be used in place of the whole series. It divides a series into two groups. The deviation on both of the sides is equal and some.

$$M = A + \frac{\sum fx}{N} \times Ci$$

Here:-

M = Mean

\sum = Sum off

x = mid point

f = Frequency

N = Total Number

CI = Class Interval

2. Standard Deviation :-

It is the square root of the mean of the squares of individual deviations from the mean in a series.

$$S_D(\sigma) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum fx^2}{N} - \left[\frac{\sum fx}{N}\right]^2}$$

Here:-

σ = Sign of standard deviation

Σ = Sum off

CI= Class Interval

d = Deviation of mid point

f = Frequency

N= Total Number

3. Standard Error Deviation :-

$$S_{ED} = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_1^2}{N_1} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{N_2}}$$

Here :-

σ_1 = SD of 1st group

σ_2 = SD of 2nd group

N_1 = Total of Sample one

N_2 = Total of Sample two

4. t-Test

A test was applied to measure the significance of differentiation between the attitudes of different part of hypothesis.”

$$t = \frac{(M_1 - M_2)}{S_{ED}}$$

Here:-

M_1 = Mean of Data No 1

M_2 = Mean of Data No 1

S_{ED} = Standard Error Deviation

5. Degree of Freedom:-

$$df = (N1+N2-2)$$

Here :-	df	-	Degree of Freedom
	N1	-	Number of Sample (According Hypothesis)
	N2	-	Number of Sample (According Hypothesis)

6. One Way ANOVA

The one-way ANOVA (“analysis of variance”) compares the means of the groups you are interested in and determines whether any of those means are statistically different from each other. Or we can say it compares the means of three or more independent groups to determine if there is a statistically significant difference between the corresponding population means.

USES OF ANOVA

- Analysis of variance is suitable technique for the interpretation of multi-dimensional variables in researches of social sciences.
- It analyses various factors and their effects in the experimentation systematically.
- It interprets the test of means and their relative interactions.
- It is a sound and economical parametric test widely used by researches.

4. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA:

Analysis of data deals with the analysis and discussion of findings resulting from the study in accordance with the research objectives and tasks as outlined in chapter one. The analyzed and interpretation of data were carried out in two phases. The first part resulted from the questionnaire which was analyzed quantitatively and the second was based on the results from documentary review, analyzed qualitatively by the content (thematic) analyses and interpretation. The quantitative data obtained have been analyzed using

statistical package for social science and also descriptive explanation have been undertaken where reason for justification has been cross checked off with the rich bodies knowledge in make.

Research often finds data analysis the most enjoyable part of carrying out any study since after all of the hard work and waiting get chance to find the answer the present at another opportunity for creativity. So analyzing the data and interpreting the result are 'REWARD' of the working of collecting data. Data do not, however 'speak of themselves'. They reveal that the investigator analyst can detect. So, when the new investigator attempting to collect this reward, find him alone with the data set and no idea how to proceed, the feeling may be one more of anxiety than of eager anticipation. As with most other aspects of a study, analysis and interpretation of the study should related to the study objectives and research question one of ten helpful strategy is to bring by imagining or even out liming the manuscript to be written from the data.

The usual analysis approach is to bring with descriptive analysis, to explore and gain a 'FEEL' for the data. The analyst then turn to address specific question from the study aims or hypothesis, from finding question, from studies reported in the literature and from pattern suggested by the descriptive analysis.

Before analysis being in earnest thought a considerable amount of preparatory work most usually be carried out.

“Statistics is the mathematical process of gathering, organizing and interpreting numerical data, which is one of the basic phases of the research process”.

- John W. Best.

When the knowledge is general and unanalyzed, it is usually described in vague, subjective terms. As such the information gathered is required to be carefully studied. The date collected appears to be vast, exhaustive, unclear and raw and quite intermingled. These data are then required to be analyzed and interpreted to reveal a clear picture to test the hypothesis and arrive at the conclusions. These provide a quantitative measure, as a foundation for the qualitative judgments that are essential for the solution to the problem.

“Scientific analysis assumes that behind the accumulated data there is something more important and revealing than the facts themselves”.

-P.V. Young.

Analysis is one of the most important aspects of the research. It requires a deep and intensive knowledge about the data to be analyzed. The researcher has to have good judgment skill, ability of generalization and should be familiar with the background objects and hypothesis of the study. Analysis is therefore the process in which the relationship or differences supporting or conflicting with the original or new hypothesis should be subjected to statistical tests of significance to determine with what validity data can be said to indicate any conclusions. It involves a number of operations which are performed with the purpose of summarizing the collected data and organizing these in a manner that they answer the research questions. Data, facts and figures are silent and they never speak for themselves but they have complexities. It is through systematic analysis that characteristics of the problem hidden in the data are revealed and valid generalizations are drawn.

“The function of systematic analysis is to build an intellectual edifice in which properly sorted and shifted facts and figures are placed in their appropriate settings and broader generalizations beyond the immediate contents of the facts under study, consistent relationships, so that general inferences can be drawn from them, which is the aim of a mature science”.

-P.V. Young.

“Interpretation takes the result of the analysis, makes inferences pertinent to the research relation studied, and draws conclusions about these relations.”

- Kerlinger

Interpretation of the data aims at drawing of inferences from the collected facts after the analytic study of the problem. It is extremely useful and important part of the study because it makes all possible use of the collected facts. Statistical facts by themselves have no utility. It is the interpretation that makes it possible for us to utilize collected data in various fields of activity.

Interpretation is by no means a mechanical process. It requires a critical, examination of the results of one's analysis in the light of the limitations of the data gathering. As such it is a vital step and a part of the research process.

Thus, statistics is not merely a device for collecting numerical data but as a means of sound techniques for their handling, analysis and drawing valid inferences from them. When the data are collected, edited, classified and tabulated, they are analyzed and interpreted with the help of various statistical techniques and tools depending upon the nature of the investigation.

4.1 TABULATION OF DATA:

Tabulation is the process of transferring data gathering instruments to the tabular form in which they are systematically examinee. Tabulation involves the orderly and systematic presentation of numerical data in a form designed to elucidate the problem under consideration. Tabulation as a final stage collection and compilation of the data is a sort of strapping stone to the analysis and interpretation of the figures.

Its main objectives are to summarize large and complex information and to present it in the simplest possible form consistent with the purpose for which it is designed. It makes the data readily comprehensible and facilitates comparison by classifying data into suitable groups. It also facilitates the detection of the errors and omission in the data.

4.2 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF THE DATA:

Statistic in the basic tools of measurement and the research efferent statistical methods pertinent to formulated hypotheses are used to verify those hypotheses.

4.3 DATA ANALYSIS:

An important aspect of analysis of data the purpose of presentation of data is to highlight the result and to make data presentation of data on result is simple and easy to understand. The graphical pictorial presentation provide a geometrical image of data

enabling to the frequency distribution and helping in observing the assumption of the statistical analysis applied for the treatment data.

4.4 ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA:

H₀₁ There is no significant mean difference on teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Good and Average work environment.

Table-4.1

Teaching efficiency of the Teachers belongs to good and average work environment

S.No.	Category	N	Mean	SD	SED	t-test Value	df	Significance Level	Interpretation
1	teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Good work environment	20	206.85	63.62	15.08	3.18	97	0.05 = 1.98	Ho1 Rejected
2	Teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Average work environment	79	158.77	44.74				0.01 = 2.62	

Interpretation: The above table shows that, the obtained ‘t’ value i.e. 3.18 is more than the table value with df - 97 at .05 level i.e 1.98 and .01 level i.e. 2.62. It means teachers belongs to High and average Work Environment differs significantly in their Work environment. Hence the Hypotheses No-1 There is no significant mean difference on teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Good and Average work environment is rejected.

Result:-There is significant mean difference on teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Good and Average work environment.

H₀₂ There is no significant mean difference on teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Good and Poor work environment.

Table-4.2

Teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Good and Poor work environment

S.No.	Category	N	Mean	SD	SED	t-test Value	df	Significant level	Interpretation
1	teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Good work environment	20	206.85	63.62	15.51	5.37	39	0.05 = 2.02	HO ₂ Rejected
2	Teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to poor work environment	21	123.42	28.42				0.01 = 2.70	

Interpretation :-The above table shows that, the obtained ‘t’ value i.e. 5.37 is more than the table value with df - 39 at .05 level i.e 2.02 and .01 level i.e 2.70 It means teachers belongs to good and poor Work Environment differs significantly in their Work environment . Hence the Hypotheses No-2 There is no significant mean difference on teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Good and Poor work environment is rejected.

Result:-There is significant mean difference on teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Good and Poor work environment. .

HO₃ There is no significant mean difference on teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Average and Poor work environment.

Table-4.3

Teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Average and Poor work environment

S.No.	Category	N	Mean	SD	SED	t-test Value	df	Significant level	Interpretation
1	Teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to average work environment	79	158.77	44.74	7.98	4.42	98	0.05 = 1.98	HO ₃ Rejected

2	Teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to poor work environment	21	123.42	28.42				0.01 = 2.62
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Interpretation :- The above table shows that, the obtained ‘t’ value i.e. 4.42 is more than the table value with $df = 98$ at .05 level i.e 1.98 and .01 level i.e 2.62 It means teachers belongs to Average and Poor Work Environment differs significantly in their Work environment . Hence the Hypotheses No-3 There is no significant mean difference on teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Average and poor work environment is rejected.

Result:- There is significant mean difference on teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Average and poor work environment.

HO-4 There is no interactional effect of work environment (good, average and poor) on teaching efficiency of the teachers.

Table-4.4

Work environment(good, average and poor) on teaching efficiency of the teachers

Summary of ANOVA

Sources of Variation	Df	SS	MS	F	Significance
Between	(k-1) 3-1=2	88057.55	44028.77	22.03	Sig.
Within	(N-K) 120-3=117	233817.25	1998.43		

df=2/117

.05= 3.09

.01= 4.82

Interpretation:-

The above table shows that, the obtained ‘f’ value for the interactional effect of teachers coming from good, average and poor work environment on teaching efficiency of the

teachers was found to be 22.03 which is more than the table value with $df=2/117$ both at .05 level i.e. 3.09 and .01 level i.e. 4.82. This indicates that teachers coming from good, average and poor work environment differ significantly in their teaching efficiency. Hence the Hypotheses No-4, There is no interactional effect of work environment (good, average and poor) on teaching efficiency of the teachers is rejected.

5. FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS:

After processing the data, obtaining and interpreting the in previous chapter, the findings have delineated and discussed in present chapter. These findings can be generalized to the extent of representativeness of the sample and methodology employed in the study. In this chapter, the results are discussed to show how this findings are concurrent with some of the empirical studies already conducted in the field. At places, some of the observation did not concur with the findings of some investigators. In such cases, attempt have been made to fathom plausible reasons for these disagreements, Keeping the major findings in view, the educational implications of the study have been worked out. But these findings do not fit in all the areas of the study. As such some suggestion have been given for the further research. This chapter therefore is devoted to focusing the findings, conclusions, discussion of the result in this study and suggestion for further studies or research.

The investigator through the present survey has studied. The purpose of this study was to examine the influence of working environment in the teaching efficiency of primary school teacher. The main findings of the present study are given below:

5.1 MAIN FINDINGS:

Ho₁ There is no significant mean difference on teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Good and Average work environment.

Findings- There is significant mean difference on teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Good and Average work environment.

Ho₂: There is no significant mean difference on teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Good and Poor work environment.

Findings- There is significant mean difference on teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Good and Poor work environment

Ho3: There is no significant mean difference on teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Average and Poor work environment.

Findings- There is significant mean difference on teaching efficiency of the teachers belongs to Average and Poor work environment.

Ho4: There is no interactional effect of Good, Average and Poor work environment on teaching efficiency of Primary School Teachers.

Findings- There is interactional effect of Good, Average and Poor work environment on teaching efficiency of Primary School Teachers.

5.2 SUGGESTIONS:

1. The govt. must provide free quarters within school campus to avoid the residential problems.
2. Separate library rooms should be opened in each school.
3. Computer education should be given in primary schools and well trained computer teachers should be appointed.
4. Adequate number of peon should be appointed in primary schools.
5. All schools should be electrified.
6. The primary school should be provided with special text books and other study materials.
7. Teachers should be avoided from politics.
8. The government must provide salaries and other payments regularly.
9. Due provision should be made in order to maintain a better administration and supervision in the schools.

5.3 EDUCATION IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY:

Following are the implications of the study

- **IMPLICATIONS FOR RESEARCH SCHOLARS:** Research scholars of Education and Psychology can be benefited by the findings of the present study. Findings of the present study will serve as a basic data for the further studies related to teachers teaching.

- **IMPLICATION FOR POLICY MAKERS:** Findings of the present study will provide feedback to policy makers and authorities concerned with teachers teaching at any level. The present situation in the educational world appears to be in the state of anomie that's why teachers seem to be alienated from the system. Professor J. N. Kapoor, a former Vice Chancellor wrote: "Many teachers are dissatisfied with the condition under which they have to work. They teach only because they have to cash their salaries and not because they enjoy teaching process. There are many other reasons for teachers being alienated from the system." He has added, in the absence of academic satisfaction for the teacher, the only other satisfaction, which the teachers seek, is the salary satisfaction and they only struggle for this.
- **IMPLICATIONS FOR PRINCIPALS:** Principals can also be benefited by the finding of the study in terms of making improvement in emotional intelligence and professional commitment. By this they can attract the teachers' devotion and dedication for their institution which will ultimately work as the measure of quality improvement in education.
- **IMPLICATIONS FOR TEACHERS:** By going through the findings of the study teachers can also take initiatives for the improvement of overall environment of their schools by which they can experience themselves well committed in their job which results in an experience of effective teaching in place of burden. If they increase their professional commitment, teacher effectiveness will be increasing automatically and they will get the self-satisfaction.

5.4 SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCHES:

Research is a continuous process and there is no end of it. Keeping in view this fact in mind the following areas are suggested for further researchers:

1. The extent and variation of Emotional Intelligence and Professional commitment of teachers at different levels of education e.g. primary and higher education should be studied separately as well as from a comparative point of view.
2. There is a need for searching other background variables like age, caste category, academic career, socio-Economic status, community

background, length of teaching experience and determine variables as principals' style of leadership, types of management etc.

3. The relationship of Emotional Intelligence and Professionally commitment with job satisfaction, burnout, and job involvement should be traced out.
4. It is been felt that the phenomenon of academic anomie be investigated and its relationship with Professional Intelligence and commitment of teachers be traced out.
5. A study of teachers' alienation and its relationship with emotional intelligence and professional commitment may also yield fruitful results.

While summing up the present study, we would like to acknowledge the fact that a scientific Endeavour in any field of study is an on-going process. Hence, we do not propose to claim any finality in regard to either to facts gathered or to the inferences drawn. The present study in its own limited way has, however made its share towards the process of building up a solid knowledge base regarding Emotional Intelligence, professional commitment and teacher effectiveness in education. If it succeeds in provoking further research in the field, its efforts would be fructified.

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